

DATA DRIVEN ANALYSIS OF TRUSS STRUCTURES BY DEEP LEARNING

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Abstract. *In this manuscript a new approach to optimum weight design of truss structures with discrete variables is described. The new algorithm is presented based on the machine learning technique. There are three steps are needed to train neural networks and produce new design variable candidates. Moreover, three kinds of neural network structures, namely, regression, multi-class classification, and binary classification, are used to compose the system. Once the neural networks are trained, the optimization cycle needs only the stress or displacement constraints. The constraints are then applied on the proposed system to obtain minimum design results. The algorithm is tested on well-known truss structures and is compared with the results of analysis. The numerical examples show that the proposed method is able to obtain minimum design results, and it is totally different way for size optimization problems.*

Keywords: *machine learning, AI, multi - classification, truss optimization, regression.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada diskret o'zgaruvchilarga ega bo'lgan ferma konstruksiyalarining optimal og'irlik dizayniga yangi yondashuv asosida tasvirlangan. Yangi algoritm MACHINE LEARNING texnikasi asosida taqdim etilgan. Bularni amalga oshirish asosan uchta qismni uz ichiga oladi. Bundan tashqari, tizimni yaratish uchun uch turdagi neyron tarmoq tuzilmalari, ya'ni rregression, ko'p sinfli tasniflash va ikkilik tasniflashdan foydalaniladi. Neyron tarmoqlari ishlashi amalga oshgandan so'ng, optimallashtirish tsikliga kuchlanish yoki joy masofaga oid cheklovlar kiritiladi. Keyinchalik minimal dizayn natijalarini olish uchun hosil bo'lgan tizimda cheklovlar qo'llaniladi. Algoritmida asosan ferma strukturasi sinovdan o'tkaziladi va tahlil natijalari bilan taqqoslanadi. Raqamli misollar shuni ko'rsatadiki, taklif qilingan usul minimal dizayn natijalarini olish qobiliyatiga ega va bu o'lchamlarni optimallashtirish muammolari uchun butunlay yangi usul bo'lib xizmat qiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *suniy intellekt, ko'p sinfli tasniflash, fermalarni optimallashtirish, regressiya.*

Introduction

The increase of interest in neural networks is obviously according to their conveniences for learning; make decision and having summaries by partial information. These features related to human brain's processes which other computer technologies have failed to pretend. As a result, one of the names that deep learning has gone by is Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and it is inspired by the biological brain. ANNs includes many nonlinear computational elements that form the network nodes, connected by weighted interconnections. Today, deep learning is the most attractive field for all spheres of engineering. In this paper, three neural networks is trained step by step in order to show developed methods of deep learning to structural optimization problems, and also illustrates results. We demonstrate innovative methods for training using hyper parameters and dropout algorithms in structural analysis in the case of ten bar truss problem. This work provides the information using more hidden layers with dropout on each layer and suitable activation functions for chosen problem. The key features in this study are neural network using linear regression algorithm and classification. In addition, dependence of

input data in achieving better accuracy is described by numerical implementation. Truss optimization problems are accomplished by several methods like differential algorithm (DE), firefly algorithm (FA), symbiotic organisms search (SOS) and so on. And each of them has some abilities for overcoming problems in the optimization process. As a basic information, cross-sectional areas, shape parameters of structural members are considered as design variables which include two groups as discrete and continuous. For design or optimization case, most usable variables are discrete variables. Hence, in this work, truss optimization with discrete variables is performed. Usually, in truss optimization, cross-sectional areas are often considered as discrete design variables and the problem is desired to minimize the weight of the structure with the satisfaction of constraints to its behavior. The mathematical expression of the truss optimization problem can be defined as follows:

$$\text{Minimize: weight } (\mathbf{A}) = \sum_{i=1}^e \rho_i l_i A_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, e$$

$$\text{subject to: } \delta_{\min} \leq \delta_j \leq \delta_{\max}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

$$\sigma_{\min} \leq \sigma_i \leq \sigma_{\max}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, e$$

$$\sigma_k^b \leq \sigma_k \leq 0, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, nc$$

$$A_i \in \mathbf{S} = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_d\}$$

Figure 1: 25 bar planar truss

Neural Network

By looking its history, it is known that deep learning is a quite novel promotion in neural network (NN) programming with representation of methods in training deep NNs. Primarily NN with more than two layers is called deep neural network. The term of NN firstly introduced by McCulloch and Pitts (1943) who derived theorems of models in neural systems similar to biological structures. The previous model of NN was called perceptron which contains of a single layer of neurons connected by weights. Rosenblatt (1958) discovered the algorithm called back propagation, but it was slow with increasing of layers.

Numerical Implementation

In this part, numerical calculations demonstrated by the library Keras (Cholet, 2015) in Python 3.6. This process includes three neural network trainings: two classification and one regression neural networks. The goal of previous NN is determine the candidates for areas by predicting on given conditions and Feed forward neural network is defined with two hidden layers. In this case input variables are stresses of each element and output is cross sectional areas of members and each output has three or more choices depending on number of classes. Figure 2 defines the training accuracies in the case of various number of hidden layers. As it is shown NN with two and three hidden layers insists almost the same accuracy. For our training, NN with two hidden layers is chosen for reducing time.

As 25 bar truss problem described in Figure 1. is well known problem in structural optimization an investigated in many researches. And in this work , truss problemm is demonstrated to describe the capability of deep learning to structural optimization. And Table 1 describes the material properties, variable bounds for the cross sectional areas for displacement and stress constraints. In this example two kind of constraints are used: firstly, σ_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, i, \dots$

,25) and d_i ($i = 18$) on six nodes in three dimensions , second one is just displacement constraints.

Property	SI unit	U.S. Customary unit
Young's modulus (E)	$68.9 \times 10^9 \text{ N/m}^2$	10^7 psi
Density (ρ)	2770.0 kg/m^3	0.1 lbm/in^3
Length (L)	190.5 cm	75.0 in
Lower bound of cross-sectional area	0.645 cm^2	0.1 in^2
Upper bound of cross-sectional area	21.935 cm^2	3.4 in^2
Allowable stress for lower nodes	$\pm 172.37 \times 10^6 \text{ N/m}^2$	$\pm 40.0 \text{ ksi}$
Allowable stress for upper nodes	$\pm 34.474 \times 10^6 \text{ N/m}^2$	$\pm 8.0 \text{ ksi}$

Table 1: Physical properties of the 25 – bar truss structure.

In 25-bar truss, creating dataset is also achieved by using FEM and different amount of datasets is compared in the case of various classes. Cross sectional areas of each element are categorized with respect to following 8 groups (1)A1; (2)A2 – A5; (3)A6 – A9; (4)A10 – A11; (5)A12 – A13; (6)A14 – A17; (7)A18 – A21; (8)A22 – A25. And cross sectional areas are used as output layer while 25 stresses with 18 displacements or just 18 displacements are input layers. Moreover, two amount of datasets is trained for checking in gaining better accuracy results. In datasets, areas are chosen randomly according to three type of classes dependently on constraints. Case 1, for just displacement constraint which is limited to ± 0.35 in on 6 nodes in three directions, classes are described in three amount which are 3 classes, 5 classes and 8 classes. Case 2, for stress constraints limited on ± 40.0 ksi on lower part of truss structure including 13 elements while ± 8.0 ksi for upper part of the structure consisting 12 elements and additional displacement constraints on nodes 6 which is limited on ± 0.35 in, classes are described in three amount which are 3 classes, 5 classes and 8 classes. In this datasets, in order to rescale the dataset into the ranges between 0 and 1, stresses are normalized by dividing allowable stress. In the case of displacement, it doesn't need to be rescaled as they involve small unit. Dataset describes above is used for all training except training 3. For training 3, datasets are created by using the prediction results of training 1 and training 2.

Figure 1: Architecture of the neural network for the 25-bar truss.

Prediction of stresses with results of Analysis. (8-100-200-43) architecture with 0.001 dropout on previous hidden layer and sigmoid activation function

Input data	Output data	Analysis	Prediction (NN)	E_{MSE}
A_1	σ_1	0.1151	0.1177	0.00001
A_2	σ_2	-0.1284	-0.1278	
A_3	σ_3	0.1225	0.1222	
A_4	σ_4	0.1225	0.1224	
A_5	σ_5	-0.1284	-0.1278	
A_6	σ_6	-0.1240	-0.1261	
A_7	σ_7	0.0895	0.0920	
A_8	σ_8	-0.124	-0.1261	
A_9	σ_9	0.0895	0.0922	
A_{10}	σ_{10}	-0.1159	-0.1132	
A_{11}	σ_{11}	-0.1159	-0.1131	
A_{12}	σ_{12}	-0.0631	-0.0648	
A_{13}	σ_{13}	-0.0631	-0.0648	
A_{14}	σ_{14}	-0.0663	-0.0666	
A_{15}	σ_{15}	-0.0068	-0.0083	
A_{16}	σ_{16}	-0.0068	-0.0083	
A_{17}	σ_{17}	-0.0663	-0.0665	
A_{18}	σ_{18}	-0.2538	-0.2563	
A_{19}	σ_{19}	0.2050	0.2008	
A_{20}	σ_{20}	0.2050	0.2009	
A_{21}	σ_{21}	-0.2538	-0.2560	
A_{22}	σ_{22}	0.0268	0.0226	
A_{23}	σ_{23}	-0.0636	-0.0688	
A_{24}	σ_{24}	0.0268	0.0226	
A_{25}	σ_{25}	0.0268	-0.0687	

Table 2: Prediction of stresses with results of Analysis. (8-100-200-43) architecture with 0.001 dropout on Input data previous hidden layer and sigmoid activation function

Conclusion

According to recent papers and research, deep learning approach on structural analysis is getting relevant. In this work, we indicated a neural network as a potential tool for truss optimization without using structural analyzers. Three neural network models are examined. Firstly, by multi classification neural network we can easily predict the optimum areas by using tanh, relu, sigmoid activation functions in training part. In the case of classification problem, binary cross entropy was used with Adam optimizer. For avoiding overfitting, dropout was applied to each hidden layer. We trained the datasets of three, five and nine classes which three classes dataset showed best accuracy. Secondly, neural network using regression provides a

model which serves for predicting stresses. Then using two neural networks we created the dataset for training next neural network which allows to predict the areas including minimum weight and satisfaction for stress constraints.

In future, deep learning approach in truss optimization can show better performance than structural optimization tools by its time consuming and accurate results by dependence on the problem.

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